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IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF RESOURCE UTILIZATION IN METALLURGICAL ENTERPRISES: INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE AND MODERN DEVELOPMENT TRENDS

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Abstract: The article examines modern approaches to improving the economic efficiency of resource utilization in metallurgical enterprises. Particular attention is paid to technological modernization, energy efficiency, digitalization of production processes, and implementation of resource-saving technologies. The study analyzes international industrial practices and identifies the main directions for improving resource management systems in the metallurgical sector.

Keywords: economic efficiency, metallurgy, resources, energy efficiency, digitalization, labor productivity, modernization.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada metallurgiya korxonalarida resurslardan foydalanish iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirishning zamonaviy yondashuvlari ko'rib chiqilgan. Texnologik modernizatsiya, energiya samaradorligi, ishlab chiqarish jarayonlarini raqamlashtirish va resurs tejovchi texnologiyalarni joriy etish masalalari tadqiq etilgan. Xalqaro sanoat tajribasi asosida metallurgiya tarmog'ida resurslarni boshqarish tizimini takomillashtirishning asosiy yo'nalishlari aniqlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: iqtisodiy samaradorlik, metallurgiya, resurslar, energiya samaradorligi, raqamlashtirish, mehnat unumdorligi, modernizatsiya.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются современные подходы к повышению экономической эффективности использования ресурсов на металлургических предприятиях. Исследуются вопросы технологической модернизации, энергоэффективности, цифровизации производственных процессов и внедрения ресурсосберегающих технологий. Особое внимание уделяется международному опыту промышленно развитых стран в области повышения эффективности производства. На основе сравнительного анализа определены основные направления совершенствования системы управления ресурсами в металлургической отрасли.

Ключевые слова: экономическая эффективность, металлургия, ресурсы, энергоэффективность, цифровизация, производительность труда, модернизация

INTRODUCTION

The metallurgical industry remains one of the most resource-intensive sectors of the global economy. High energy consumption, significant raw material costs, and environmental pressures force enterprises to search for new approaches to improving production efficiency. In modern conditions, economic competitiveness increasingly depends on the ability of enterprises to optimize resource utilization and implement innovative industrial technologies.

According to the World Steel Association, global steel production exceeded 1.8 billion tonnes in recent years, while the industry accounts for nearly 7–8% of global carbon emissions [1]. These conditions require industrial enterprises to modernize production systems and adopt energy-efficient technologies.

At the same time, digital transformation and industrial automation are becoming major drivers of productivity growth. Countries actively investing in industrial modernization demonstrate higher levels of resource efficiency and lower production losses.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The issue of improving economic efficiency in industrial enterprises has been widely discussed in modern economic and industrial research. Contemporary studies increasingly focus on resource productivity, sustainable industrial development, and technological modernization as key factors of industrial competitiveness.

Michael Hammer and James Champy emphasized that business process reengineering and organizational transformation play a crucial role in increasing industrial productivity and reducing operational costs [2]. Their research demonstrated that enterprises implementing process optimization achieve higher levels of efficiency and resource utilization.

In addition, Joseph Stiglitz highlighted the importance of technological innovation and institutional support in ensuring sustainable economic growth. According to Stiglitz, industrial efficiency largely depends on the ability of enterprises to adapt to technological changes and improve management systems [3].

Furthermore, studies conducted by Dani Rodrik show that industrial modernization and structural transformation are among the main drivers of productivity growth in developing economies [4]. Rodrik argues that manufacturing industries remain central to long-term economic development due to their strong technological and productivity spillover effects.

Similarly, research by Jeffrey Sachs focuses on sustainable industrial development and resource efficiency. Sachs notes that modern industrial systems must combine economic growth with rational resource management and environmental sustainability [5].

At the same time, researchers from the International Energy Agency and UNIDO emphasize that heavy industries, including metallurgy, remain among the most energy-intensive sectors of the global economy. According to the organization's reports, technological modernization and energy-efficient production systems are capable of significantly reducing industrial energy consumption and production losses [6,7].

Moreover, their studies indicate that industrial digitalization. Thus, the literature demonstrates that improving economic efficiency requires a comprehensive approach combining technological innovation, organizational transformation, energy efficiency, and digital industrial development.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research is based on comparative and statistical analysis of international industrial practices in the metallurgical sector. Data from international organizations, scientific publications, and industrial reports were used.

The methodology includes:

- analysis of scientific and analytical literature;
- comparative evaluation of industrial modernization strategies;
- analysis of energy efficiency indicators;
- assessment of productivity and resource utilization trends in selected countries.

The study focuses on Germany, Japan, China and South Africa due to their significant role in global steel production and industrial innovation.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Countries implementing technological modernization programs achieve higher levels of industrial productivity and resource efficiency.

According to the World Steel Association, the global steel industry consumed approximately 21.27 GJ of energy per tonne of crude steel in 2023, while material efficiency reached 98.15%. These indicators confirm the increasing importance of technological innovation in reducing industrial costs.

The analysis of international metallurgical practices demonstrates that improvements in resource efficiency are primarily achieved through technological modernization, energy restructuring, and large-scale industrial digitalization (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Main directions for improving economic efficiency in metallurgical enterprises¹

A clear example is the steel industry of the European Union, particularly Germany, where the transition toward Industry 4.0 has significantly improved production efficiency. According to the International Energy Agency (IEA), energy efficiency policies combined with scrap-based steel production have enabled a reduction in energy intensity compared to traditional blast furnace routes, since secondary steelmaking requires considerably less energy input than primary production. In addition, the shift toward electric arc furnace (EAF) technology in developed economies has been identified as one of the key drivers of lower emissions intensity in steel production [6].

Similarly, Japan demonstrates a different but equally effective model of efficiency improvement. Japanese metallurgical enterprises, such as Nippon Steel, widely implement lean production systems and continuous improvement (Kaizen) principles. These approaches focus on minimizing production waste, improving process stability, and enhancing labor productivity. As a result, Japan maintains one of the highest levels of material utilization efficiency in the global steel industry, despite limited domestic raw material resources [6].

In contrast, China presents a case of large-scale production-driven efficiency transformation. According to World Steel Association, China accounted for approximately 50% of global crude steel output in recent years, exceeding 1 billion tonnes annually. However, studies show that this rapid expansion has historically been associated with high energy consumption and environmental pressure. At the same time, recent industrial policies have shifted toward capacity reduction, modernization of outdated plants, and increased adoption of energy-efficient technologies such as electric arc furnaces and digital process control systems.

For example, data from the International Energy Agency indicate that the steel sector accounts for about 7–8% of global energy system emissions, making it one of the most carbon-intensive industries worldwide. In response, countries such as China have begun restructuring their steel production base by closing inefficient plants and promoting “green steel” initiatives. This has led to gradual improvements in energy efficiency indicators, although structural challenges remain due to the dominance of blast furnace-based production [6].

Another important dimension is the role of scrap-based steel production. According to research published in Resources, Conservation and Recycling, secondary steelmaking (using scrap in electric arc furnaces) is significantly more energy-efficient than primary ore-based production, with efficiency levels more than twice as high in some cases. This supports the global transition toward circular economy principles in metallurgy, where material recycling becomes a central mechanism of resource optimization (Table 1) [8].

¹ Compiled by the author

Table 1. Resource Efficiency Measures in Selected Countries²

Country	Main Industrial Strategy	Practical results
Japan	Lean production and waste minimization	Higher productivity and lower operational costs
Germany	Smart manufacturing and automation	Reduction of production losses and improved energy efficiency
China	Large-scale industrial modernization and digitalization	Growth in steel output and export competitiveness
South Africa	Energy efficiency modernization in heavy industry	Reduction of industrial energy consumption by 10–12%

South Africa pays significant attention to improving energy efficiency in mining and metallurgical industries due to the high energy intensity of industrial production. According to reports from the UNIDO, modernization of industrial equipment and implementation of energy-saving technologies have helped several enterprises reduce electricity consumption and operational costs.

Another important trend is the growing role of industrial digitalization. Modern enterprises increasingly use automated resource management systems, predictive maintenance technologies, and industrial analytics platforms. These technologies improve operational control and reduce downtime in production systems [8].

The research also demonstrates that industrial competitiveness increasingly depends on sustainable resource management strategies. Enterprises that actively invest in modernization and innovation achieve better long-term economic performance and stronger market positions [9].

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Improving the economic efficiency of resource utilization is one of the key conditions for sustainable industrial development. International experience shows that technological modernization, digitalization, and energy-efficient production systems significantly improve productivity and reduce industrial costs.

The experience of Germany, Japan, South Africa and China demonstrates that effective resource management contributes not only to higher industrial competitiveness but also to long-term sustainability of metallurgical enterprises. In modern conditions, successful industrial development requires a comprehensive approach combining technological innovation, digital transformation, and rational use of production resources [9,10].

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